

The lived experience of educators in the online class for S.Y. 2020-2021

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Abstract

The effects of COVID-19 pandemic have affected the education system in the Philippines. The need for new innovative learning techniques has become an integral part of the education system. Due to the changes in education, the teachers had a hard time teaching in an online class. As educators, they are responsible for the students' learning and development in able to promote active learning in their classes. The study used the descriptive phenomenology of research through online and face-to-face interviews to examine the experiences of educators in the online class setup. Purposive sampling was used as a sampling scheme. Twenty (20) educators in social studies at the secondary education who are teaching in public high schools was the respondents. In terms of interpretation and analysis, this study used transcendental descriptive phenomenology. The results of the study are manifestations of the community of inquiry theory that includes teaching presence in the mode of instructions, different learning environments, and struggles of educators, under the cognitive presence in a form of online classroom discussion, forms of assessment, consultation and parental involvement, then in the social presence in a form of feedback to learners, collaborative learning, sense of encouragement, and assessment of the learners which are anchored to the statement of the problem of the study to get the educational experience where the online class takes place. This implies that many challenges and hurdles that educators had while utilizing an online course, as a result, they utilize a range of online teaching tactics to better their teaching methods, and despite the epidemic, many of them still see learning as crucial. According to the study, education professionals and school administrators may assist instructors in developing additional tactics and procedures to meet the numerous problems they face while shifting to new teaching methods.

Keywords: Transcendental descriptive; Phenomenology; Collaborative learning; Innovative learning; Purposive sampling; Community of inquiry.

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To cite this article:

Cinco, J. C. L., Malig-on, S. E., Mateo Jr., N. G., Rosaldo, R. A. C., Sta. Ana, J. L. P., & Romero, J. A. (2022). The lived experience of educators in the online class for S.Y. 2020-2021. *SDCA Asia-Pacific Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 4 (1), 34-39.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic characterizes the worldwide well-being crisis within recent memory and the most significant challenge faced since World War Two (BBC, 2020). Since its manifestation in Asia at the end of 2019, the infection has spread all over the world. This now arrived at the grievous achievement of millions of deaths and still increasing, and the human race is enduring a terrible weight of misfortune. As stated by the United Nations Development Programme (2020), the climbing loss of life is faltering, and everyone should cooperate in reducing the spread of this infection. Every nation requires to work directly to plan, respond, and heal; however, Covid-19 pandemic is much more than a health issue, it is also unprecedented how different sectors of every nation are affected, specifically the economy.

As stated by Wilson (2020), the year 2020 would take the title of being the worst year in modern history because of the COVID-19 pandemic, natural calamities, and many challenges that the world is currently facing. As a result of this pandemic to flatten the curve, restrictions on non-essential movements of people across globe were imposed by government. In the Philippines, the entire island of Luzon and other provinces were placed under enhanced community quarantine as the country increased its number of infected cases in March 2020. The Philippines was also placed under State of Public Health Emergency and the State of Calamity as the nation continues its struggle toward the COVID-19 pandemic.

As of March 2020, the start of community quarantine brought millions of children. Students have been constrained out of schools, from elementary up to college level, the government forced to localize school closures.

Due to the stipulations inflicted on mass gatherings, face-to-face classes for the school year 2020-2021 in the Philippines were suspended. This restriction forced all education institutions to shift to flexible and distance learning. As stated by Simbulan (2020), since face-to-face classes and mass gatherings were prohibited, higher education institutions (HEIs) on both public and private schools have to adjust to the new system of education. Teachers and administrators worked together to revise and adapt course syllabi and requirements as the Philippine education system shifted to alternative or remote teaching modalities for both synchronous and asynchronous. Learners and educators need to have access to electronic devices and reliable Internet connectivity. This shift will use applications such as Skype, Zoom, Google Chat, Blackboard, Moodle, and Canvas as learning management systems. If the teachers and students have limited access to computers or unreliable access to the internet, they could use Facebook Messenger and smartphones to communicate and send notes and learning materials.

As stated by Toquero et al. (2021), the government urged various groups of concerned teachers, health professionals, parents, and youth to postpone classes to 2021 due to unpreparedness. This concern is not new to the public; however, the pandemic has augmented this concern. The Philippine education system has criticized many groups long ago before the COVID-19 pandemic because of slow accommodation for students around the country. The call for the postponement of the school year and academic freeze due to alleged unpreparedness was opposed and dismissed by the Commission on Higher Education and Department of Education.

This caused several sentiments and problems regarding the online class and its quality. As stated by Arinto (2016), the predicament with online education and learning as a teaching model is that these would give the educators confusion because there are too many prospects, decisions, and ways of doing things when it comes to technological proficiency. Educators also need technical support and leadership, especially when achieving a new pedagogy. In light of this evidence, most educators in the Philippines are still adjusting to this kind of situation.

The emergence of information technology and communication has significantly reshaped the structure of learning in higher education. According to Albrahim (2020), classroom boundaries have exceeded the realms of time, location, and physical presence. It was evident and observed in the usual set-up. It is the period of anytime and anywhere learning. New instructional pedagogies, learning aptitudes, and appraisal strategies have developed to adjust to these changes. In addition, different arrangements of learning have thrived. Various programs, certificates, and degrees could be earned by attending open universities, online education, or massive open online courses. Such changes mark challenges that may affect all instructional faculty in higher education who have to keep pace with the innovative criteria of higher education, new approaches to research and accreditation, and new teaching and learning methods. This encompasses the awareness of who the learners are, what the learners want, how the students be taught, and what skills do they possess. As instructors, one needs to master to execute their role effectively. Hence, all the educators adjust to how to deliver the new lesson using online class.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to determine the lived experience of educators in Social Studies at secondary basic education who are teaching in public high schools. With the new implementation platform when it comes to education, such as the online class synergy. With the help of the researchers and their esteemed supportive advisers, it is their preliminary step in conducting a research study. The lived experience of the educators will identify the online class set-up. Notably, it intends to respond to subsequent research inquiries.

1. How do the participants perceive teaching presence in an online class?
2. How the participants describe the learning experiences through cognitive presence in an online class?
3. How do the participants promote social presence in an online class set-up?
4. What are the strategies utilized by the participants to facilitate active learning?

5. What improvement plan may be drawn from the findings of the study?

Methods

The study used the descriptive phenomenology of research through online and face-to-face interviews to examine the experiences of educators in the online class setup. The primary purpose of descriptive phenomenology research, according to Clemente et al. (2016), is to give information or newly discovered ideas which are result of exploration. It fills in the details and gaps regarding a particular idea with the intent to expand understanding with a specific phenomenon. The purpose of descriptive phenomenology is to discover information needed to be supplied to answer the statement of the problem of this study instead of formulating unsure explanations.

For the process of analyzing the responses, the researchers used Transcendental Phenomenology. As stated by van Manen (2011), Edmund's detailed phenomenology is the precise science of all credible transcendental phenomena. All information should be based on clear insights.

In line with Creswell and Poth (2016), phenomenological research defines the ordinary purpose for various people of their lived experiences of a thought or a phenom. Phenomenologists concentrate on explaining what all participants have in general as they encounter a phenomenon. The fundamental goal of phenomenology is to conquer personal lives with a phenomenon to the various universal spirit. Phenomenology is prominent in the individual and health sciences, notably in sociology.

A philosophical discussion is involving the fundamental thoughts associated with leading a phenomenology. This varies on the lived experiences of people and how others should include both subjective realities of the phenomenon and authentic experiences of something in general with other individuals (Creswell & Poth, 2016). While interpreting the responses, the researchers need to consider where they are coming from.

Epoche or bracketing is the primary step in "phenomenological modification." To take a current perspective approaching the phenomenon under study besides checking the thoughts in a contemplative movement develops curiosity (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

According to Creswell and Poth (2016), data collection is a set of related activities intended at gathering good information to answer emerging research questions. The researchers interviewed the participants to collect information. To gather the data, the researchers developed a set of rules or printed forms for noting the information needed to establish some forms for recording the data, such as an interview or observational protocols. In this study, the researchers utilized interviews to gather information and develop more understanding of the study. In line with this, in phenomenological, the data analysis is similar for all psychological phenomenologists. Constructing the data from the research questions, data analysts go through data (e.g., interview transcription) and emphasize or quote the vital statement of the participants on how the participants experienced the phenomenon. This step is called horizontalization. After that, the researchers developed a cluster of meaning from the vital statement of the participants into themes (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

In line with Neubauer et al. (2019), phenomenology is a qualitative research method that investigates to describe a person's lived experiences. The primary purpose of phenomenology is to establish the nature of experience.

The study is wrapped and limited to the responses and insights about the participants' experiences in the online class for the S.Y 2020-2021 from the educators in social studies at the secondary education who are teaching in public high schools.

As for the sampling, Canlapan and Campena (2016) claimed that the researchers classified the process of this study as a non-probability sampling, especially purposive sampling. It is the sampling done with a purpose in mind. This technique is also called judgmental or selective sampling. The researchers chose the public-school teachers handling Social Studies at secondary level because it is believed that they are the best-fitted individuals to answer the research questions.

Result and Discussion

1. The perception of educators in an online class

Educators worldwide witnessed a remarkable transition to online education that will test the educational setting. In Philippine education, the start of classes was prolonged to allow participants and students to adapt to the *different learning environment*. That is why the participants experience quite defamiliarization with the use of online class rather than face-to-face. The online class is different from traditional classroom instruction that requires the participants to various educational training and development. Correspondingly, participants indicated that they need a lot of planning for the various learning modalities in terms of online class. Exploring other novel learning modalities that will facilitate migration from conventional to flexible pedagogy and education has become an urgent responsibility of the participants. Also, according to the participants' responses, they found it challenging to educate the learners in an online class because of the *mode of instruction*. For instance, the teacher must retain all of the information in terms of the delivery of the subject. They are having difficulty delivering the lesson, evaluating the learners, providing the learning tasks, encouraging the students' learning, and getting the learners' attention. In addition, the participants are *struggling*, which points to the contrast between the face-to-face class and online classes. Participants stated that adjusting to the new standard education is difficult for them because they are experiencing problems with an unreliable internet connection, lack of data, absence of attention due to disruptions, major shift in terms of technological proficiency, encouragement of the learners, *mental well-being* of the participants, and learners' priority during online class. Also, the *personal factor* and *family factor* are part of their struggles in an online class. As explained by Moralista and Oducado (2020), several difficulties and challenges in online education are perceived by faculty. Hence, due to the reason of shift into a new normal education, educators perceive the diverse struggles in an online class.

2. The participants' description of the learning experiences through cognitive presence in an online class

Since the implementation of online class in basic education, participants are trying many things to promote learning in *online classroom discussion* such as making a teacher script aside from the lesson planning. Providing specified and clear instructions to learners may guarantee that students can fully understand all the things that they need to achieve tasks that they need to do; hence, it will make them more productive (Barile, n.d.). Participants mostly used *visual presentation* to deliver their discussions as clear as possible so that students could comprehend it better and when it comes to the *lesson presentation* itself, the participants are doing things that will make their instructions and lesson more understandable and comprehensive for the students just like giving examples, repetition of the certain topic or instruction, asking and answering questions from the students for clarifications and translation of the instructions and lesson to the language where the students can fully understand. In part of the discussion the participants asked questions about the topic and they used *art of questioning* based on the real-world application to see if students can execution their learned knowledge in real world. Participants also assured that their students are learning. Hence, they gave different *forms of assessment* to the students to measure the acquired knowledge and skills of their students. The participants commonly used oral recitation, formative assessments, summative assessments, multiple choice, portfolio assessments, and weekly assessments. The sole purpose of these assessments made by the participants is to see the manifestation of learning of the students where it can also serve as a basis for self-evaluation on their teaching skills in the online classroom setup. Participants revealed that they were conducting consultation with their learners despite of the time restrictions to promote good communication with them. Moreover, they had meeting within the faculty members in order to decide the necessary things to do what is important in the learning process of the students in the online class. Lastly, participants emphasized the role of *parental involvement* for the students' learning development because parents/guardians are the ones who have more time with the students. This is the reason why in this new learning modality, educators are expecting more from the parents in helping the learners because they have a vital role in learning and acquiring necessary knowledge and skills of the students. Educators believe that they should have an open and good communication with the parents/guardians of the learners.

3. Educators promoting social presence in an online class set-up

In the face-to-face class setup, educators easily engage their learners in class activity. They can promote social interaction with students to learn easily. However, due to the implementation of online class in basic education, educators are trying their best to find a way on how they are going to promote social presence in their class through online. After conducting an interview and analyzing the responses of the participants, the study revealed that in the first grading of online class, the educators in basic education particularly in Araling Panlipunan, the Department struggled in promoting social presence in their class. It is revealed that the educators are still in adjustment during the first quarter of online class.

Hence, in the next quarter of online class, the participants try their best to find a strategy on how they are going to engage their learners and how they are going to build a rapport with them. In the study, it showed that the educator sees the importance of the *learner's feedback* in their online class. Participants saw the learner's feedback in their lesson which are also a learner's engagement in online class. The study also revealed the importance of learner's initiative. The collaborative learning exercises that took place in the experimental community were found to boost student motivation (Ozkara & Cakir, 2020). The initiative of the learners to have an engagement with their classmate is way of having a social presence in the class. These are the opportunities that educators see in their class to keep the social presence alive.

Furthermore, the study also shows that the participants promote social presence in their online class through *collaborative learning* by assigning groups and parent involvement in the learners' activities. Participants can create a different online class activity that promote a social presence in online class. Aside from collaborative learning between students, the study revealed that parents' involvement in learner's education during online class is also a collaborative learning. Now that the learners spend more time with their families, the educators use it to engage the learner's parent in their activities as a way of collaborative learning in online class. After analyzing the responses of the participants, it is revealed that establishing a good and friendly relationship with learners in online class is important. In online class where everyone is still adopting and adjusting to the changes in education, the encouragement of the educators plays a big role in their learner's education in online class. The relationship of the educators to their learners helps them to create a good atmosphere in the online class. Friendly atmosphere is important to online class. The *sense of encouragement* of the participants in online class is the key component to have a social presence in class. Educators must be active in their communications with learners to encourage social presence. The study revealed the role of assessment of the learners to have a social presence in online class. *Assessment of the learners* gives opportunities to the learners and teacher to collaborate with other learners and teachers like the strategy of Participant 12 and Participant 15 they used Integrative Assessment. Aside from social presence, assessment of the learners, especially the integrative assessment helps to lessen the work of the learners in online class. The educators can collaborate with other subject teachers in some activities.

4. *The strategies utilized by the participants to facilitate active learning*

In the situation right now, it is undeniable that both educators and learners are struggling in an online class setup. However, educators are still fighting to address the educational needs of the learners in the new normal of education in the country even though it is challenging for both educators and learners. 12 participants revealed that they used instructional materials such as PowerPoint presentation, text-based activity, video lesson, and drawing and coloring. According to Yang (2017), strategies for online class is composed of different approaches and methods that will gain the attention and excitement of the learners to learn in the class.

Eight participants also revealed that they used teaching strategies such as games, question-and-answer, and groupings. Participants also mentioned that they are using different learning platforms such as Google Meet, Messenger, Google Classroom, Facebook, Zoom, and even text messaging for communication and learning purposes.

5. *Improvement plan and findings from the study*

The government always had a strong hold on schools and schools have been mandated to abide by local and national laws and policies, that is why the participants, who suggested to provide strong internet connection, proposed that the *interaction of the Local Government Unit* with their services must be pursued in the continuation of the online learning of the students under their supervisions by providing strong and reliable internet connection in their localities that must be supervised and budgeted by the national government.

The whole country immediately shifted and opted to online learning which further highlighted the digital divide that is present in the country. In less than a month, various issues surfaced all over the media and on the internet with regards the connectivity problems of learners and teachers in conducting full online classes with the help and services of the *internet connection*. Moreover, regarding with the *production and distribution of the printed learning materials*, LGUs will supervise this distribution to every student who needs printed learning materials. It is a collaboration of the school and the LGUs among the concerned beneficiaries of this services. Without these government units, there will be no uniform standards, policies, rules and regulations in running a school. Furthermore, the curriculum is also prescribed by government units to ensure coherent and consistent competencies, skills, and desired outcomes from all learners, giving them equal advantages, access, and opportunities in their schooling.

Formulate *learning strategies and modalities* that will incorporate the online class either in online learning and modular distance learning to still facilitate active learning among the students. *Learning resources* for them to have an easy access must be pursued also by the supervision of the Department of Education to provide the students a good and reliable source of information that is up to date and a storage of lesson and activities that will make them feel they are learning just like in physical learning.

Lastly, *a culture of parent volunteering is also a viable way of supporting parents to help the school*. The collaboration of the school and parents in a form of *home visitation* must be pursued to motivate them and still continue learning despite the challenges by monitoring, guiding, and helping them accessing the learnings they needed to be absorbed because they are still the one who are the parents that provide learning to their children. This will lessen the workload of the teachers in honing their students' harmonious relationships which must be fostered with communities. This can be done by establishing a strong support base for the community through healthy and meaningful public relations - providing necessary aid, training, resources, and services to them. Hence, parents serve as a powerful lever for raising student achievement in schools that serve as community hubs for parent training wherein parents are given the adequate tools, resources and support in refining their skills in teaching their children.

In the final analysis for the improvements of online class, the themes held accordingly based on the participants' responses. This will lead them into improvements as a basis for future purposes to every educational institution. This research will guide educators for the learning process of their students towards engaging the virtual online class and restructure course outlines to a simple and attainable where everything is provided to the students.

Conclusion

This study concludes educators in an online class faced various problems and hurdles in the sense of online education. The majority of the educators stated that using an online course compared to a face-to-face class is unfamiliar. As a result, despite the pandemic, the value of learning can never be neglected. Furthermore, based on the participants' responses, they face trials in their preparation for learning delivery modalities. They use a range of online teaching strategies to educate themselves effectively. It was challenging for the educators to communicate with the learners because of the various difficulties in the online class. As a result of the sudden transition to entirely online instruction, the educators had to adjust their pedagogy, planning styles, and assessment purposes.

To promote the cognitive presence of the learners, educators are creating teaching scripts, presenting visual introductions to likewise, educators are giving examples, repetition, translation, and posting and noting inquiries from the learners. Likewise, in the discussion, the art of questioning is being utilized. To assess the learners' development, educators are executing different forms of assessment. Educators are having a consultation with both the learners and co-educators is additionally featured in this study. Hence, parental involvement is vital in the online classroom setup to promote the learnings of the learners.

The researchers also conclude that educators used budget friendly online applications that will not cost a lot of internet data allocation. Encouraging social presence in online classes is difficult for educators. However, by groupings, messenger group conversations, parental engagement, and alternative evaluations for the learners are the educator's technique to keep the learners' participation and have social presence in online class.

The technological tools used by educators are also typical technology tools when there are face-to-face classes. These tools are utilized because both educators and learners know how to manage and navigate it.

Recommendations

Higher offices, curriculum experts, and school authorities may collaborate with educators to overcome the problems they confront as they transition to new teaching methods. Educators should be supplied with the essential resources and training in order for them to deliver quality education properly. Educators must develop appropriate plans and techniques to meet the demands of the new normal in the teaching and learning process. They should approach the problem with a growth mindset, embrace change, and explore opportunities by getting out of their convenient zones. They must be able to achieve leadership, creativity, and innovation.

Furthermore, for educators to thrive in this challenging time and continually deliver constructive contributions to education, their mental health and well-being must constantly be protected. Therefore, the Department of Education should enhance their psychological support for the educators and the learners. Mental health is an essential concern for all educators who are usually their learners' first line of defense.

The collaboration of educators and parents must be pursued in more extensive way to motivate the learners to learn and to acquire skills. It will also help to linger learning despite the challenges by monitoring, guiding, and helping learners in acquiring the learnings they needed to be absorbed because they are still the one that provide the necessities of the learners, this will lessen the workload of the schools and serve as community hubs for parent training wherein parents are given adequate tools, resources, and support in refining their skills in teaching their children. Hence, promoting an open communication with the parent will surely address certain problems in this new learning modality. Furthermore, the researchers also recommend the use of assessment that will make the students perform and showcase their different abilities and skill so that learners can execute their strengths executing what they have learned.

DepEd should provide quality technology tools for all teaching personnel that accommodates learners this school year. The technology tools like personal computer, laptop and even internet connection will be a great tool for educators to create a quality instructional material if the department will provide these tools to ensure the facilitation of active learning. There should have a one learning management system for online classes across the country that can easily utilize, navigate, and browse by the learners and educators. Aside from the DepEd Commons, the department should also develop a learning management system for online classes that can be access by educators and learners even without internet connection or using free data only so that the learning process in this set up cannot interrupt by the slow internet connectivity.

While social presence is necessary in the face-to-face class setup, it is a challenge in the online class setting. Nevertheless, as educational institutions transition from the physical to the online environment, they continue to promote active learning by socializing using technology such as an application that is used by all netizens. Developing effective collaborative learning activities using technology with the help of different online platform that the learner can access, the educators can use it for the collaborative learning of the students in online class. With the use of different social media platform, the learners can engage themselves with other learners. However, the educators must understand the capability of the learners to understand the lesson in online class and educators must focus on enhancing their skills in different online instructional materials and pedagogy to deliver the effective collaborative learning activities to the class. Furthermore, the educators and the higher officials in education can develop the collaborative online learning in online class through promoting the collaboration of two and more subject with connected learning competencies. Through this, it can lessen the work of the learners and educators in online class.

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